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MOTIVATION FOR UPPER SECONDARY SCHOOL MATHEMATICS THROUGH WORKING LIFE CONNECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This concept paper presents an ongoing project with the aims of motivating upper secondary school students to study mathematics, communicating the importance of mathematics in different occupations to them, and persuading especially the girls to keep their options open for continuing their studies in mathematics-intensive fields, such as engineering. The basic idea of the project is to connect the upper secondary school mathematics syllabus to concrete applications of mathematics in different occupations. This is done by three means: 1) providing mathematics teachers exemplars of different occupations and working life scenarios, 2) building an online course on working life mathematics for upper secondary school students and 3) training university student ambassadors, who visit upper secondary schools and talk about the need for mathematics in different study fields and their experiences of studying mathematics in the tertiary level education.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Finnish labour market is among the most gender segregated in Europe [1]. A central part of the explanation for this phenomenon is the strong gender segregation of educational choices at the tertiary level, which, in turn, is connected to the gender segregation of subject choices at the secondary level.

Nowadays, girls constitute a majority of Finnish upper secondary school students and generally get better grades in their matriculation exams than boys [2]. One exception to this is mathematics, which boys choose more and where boys typically outperform girls in the exam [3]. All students have to choose either a long or a short syllabus in mathematics. Students choosing the long syllabus have to take a matriculation exam in mathematics, but for the students taking the short syllabus the matriculation exam in mathematics is optional. Research has shown that the competence level in mathematics of those students who only complete the minimum number of courses remains at the level they have achieved during the compulsory basic education [4]. Choosing the short syllabus in mathematics and not taking a matriculation exam in mathematics is more common among girls than boys [3]. Hence, at the end of upper secondary school, the average competence in mathematics of girls trails boys by approximately one year [4].

Yazilitas et al. [5] discovered that in the Netherlands girls often choose science and mathematics at the secondary level to keep their options open for the tertiary level studies. In Finland, the upper secondary school subject choices seem to be more exclusive, and girls commonly make choices which rule out the possibility to study for example engineering at university [2]. Instead, girls' subject choices—psychology, health education, and religion—often relate to the wish to study educational sciences, humanities or health sciences [2]. The fact that mathematics is needed also in these disciplines is not very widely acknowledged among upper secondary school students and can result in struggles in tertiary level studies, for example, when a nursing student needs to pass the exam in medical calculations.

Contextual framing of mathematics problems is a commonly proposed means to increase students' interest in mathematics. It does not come without problems [6], but the use of engineering problems in the upper secondary school mathematics teaching has been shown to increase students' perception of practicality and usefulness of mathematics [7], and the utility value of mathematics has been noted not to decrease students' intrinsic motivation for mathematics [8]. Feelings about mathematics have been noted to impact the engineers' career choices heavily [9]. Illustrating the task value of mathematics in school is commonly suggested by engineers as a means to engage young people with mathematics [9]. It has proven to be effective in increasing also engineering students' interest in mathematics [10].

This paper presents a project where the upper secondary school mathematics syllabus is amended and supported with concrete applications of mathematics in different occupations. The aim of the project is to motivate upper secondary school students to study mathematics and communicate the importance of mathematics in

different occupations especially to girls. The rest of this paper first introduces the central elements of the project and then discusses the insights we have gained during this project.

2 PROJECT “TyöMAA”

The project started in spring 2019 and will finish in summer 2022. The project activities consist of three lines of action: 1) creating teaching material for mathematics teachers, 2) building an online course for upper secondary school students and 3) training university student ambassadors.

2.1 Material for teachers

The material for teachers contains mathematical exemplars of different occupations and working life scenarios. The problem illustrations extend over several occupational areas, such as engineering, business, physiotherapy, nursing, tourism and hospitality. They have been collected in a free, open source GeoGebra software, which allows several helpful features for teaching, such as graphical illustrations or 3D demonstrations [11]. The material produced in the project is structured according to the mathematics syllabus to support the findability of relevant exemplars. The material is not yet final, and it is constantly being developed. During academic year 2020-21 there were ten teachers piloting the material.

2.2 Online course for students

The objective of the developed online course is to support students' mathematics learning throughout the course of upper secondary school. After gaining access to the course, the students can relatively freely choose the way they operate in the course as well as the timing of their studies. The study time is not limited, so the students can proceed in the course with the same pace they study the different mathematics courses in upper secondary school. The online course also provides an excellent platform for revising for the matriculation exam.

The course was planned in cooperation with upper secondary school teachers, and the course structure follows the mathematics syllabus. The course operates on a Moodle platform and uses a computer-aided assessment package STACK for the realization of the exercises. More detailed information about the course can be found in [12]. The first students started the course during summer 2020. At the end of spring 2021, there were 20 upper secondary school students (14 girls, 5 boys and 1 other, gender identified from name) enrolled on the course.

2.3 Math ambassadors

Math ambassadors are university students whose role is to motivate the upper secondary school students and to inform them about the need for mathematics in different occupations. Ambassadors visit the upper secondary schools and give about a 30 min talk, which covers the introduction of mathematical aspects in several occupations and study areas (health care, business, engineering, tourism and hospitality, arts, social work, education and psychology), as well as their personal

experiences of studying mathematics at the university level. Ambassadors are also present in the online course during certain consultation hours and answer upper secondary school students' questions on chat.

The first five visits by the math ambassadors were conducted in autumn 2020. Based on immediate feedback from the teachers, the upper secondary school students found the ambassador visits interesting and encouraging.

3 DISCUSSION

We are continuously collecting feedback on all the activities with feedback forms linked to the online course (students) and GeoGebra-material (teachers), but so far the feedback has been scarce because of the limited number of users, a relatively short user experience time, and the COVID-19 pandemic. Further feedback from the teachers will be acquired in a national workshop in autumn 2021. Although the pandemic may momentarily decrease the upper secondary school teachers' and students' interest in different kinds of online tools, we believe that in the long run, the 'forced' online learning experiences during the pandemic lower the threshold for engaging in these kinds of activities and increase the attractiveness of online resources, such as the GeoGebra material and the online course developed in the project. The current numbers of students enrolled on the online course suggest that the course is more interesting to girls than boys, which can help reduce the currently strong gender segregation in education and occupations.

Our work has shown that both GeoGebra and STACK provide good tools for building mathematics exemplars and problems contextualised in working life scenarios, but without too much simplification or 'sanitising', which is feared to obscure their efficiency in supporting the learning of mathematics [6]. We also believe that conveying the same message about the need for mathematics in different occupations through all the three means provided by the project will have an effect on the upper secondary school students' actions when choosing the subjects to be studied at the secondary level as well as the studies they will pursue in the tertiary level education. However, this belief needs still to be verified, and we are currently thinking of possibilities to study this issue further during and after the project.

After the project finishes, the GeoGebra material will be freely available for all the interested teachers, the online course will become part of the regular open university offering at LAB University of Applied Sciences, and the visits of math ambassadors will continue to be organised by the local science and technology education centre. Hence, all the activities will continue and also provide a venue for a more comprehensive research on the effectiveness of the actions than is possible during the project lifetime.

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